

A Users' Guide to Economical Digital Data Usage

1. Introduction

In the course of the technologization of almost all fields in the humanities and especially the natural sciences, increasingly large amounts of research data can be generated in shorter and shorter periods of time. Research data refers to all data generated in the course of a research project, e.g. through working with sources, experiments, measurements, surveys or simulations. At the same time, research funders' expectations towards archiving and publishing data are increasing, as outlined e.g. by the German Research Foundation in its Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice.¹ The Open Science movement strives to make all strategies, procedures and components of the research process openly accessible and reusable, thereby opening up new possibilities for research, society and the economy in dealing with research findings.² This includes data provision and reuse.

A wide range of developments can currently be observed with regard to the growing acquisition, availability, transparency and reusability of research data, which is to be welcomed in many respects. Research data management according to the FAIR principles is becoming a standard, the publication of data more and more goes without saying, and data-driven as well as data-supported research can be found in all academic disciplines. However, these developments bring with them technical and organizational challenges. These include an increase in the resources required in all phases of the research data lifecycle, both in terms of technology and personnel. In addition, legal and ethical challenges may arise.³

In view of these circumstances and through this guide, we intend to provide hands-on approaches on how to reduce the required technical and organizational resources via digital data economy.⁴ A checklist enhances these practical approaches, it offers ways to check your own data for potential cuts. It is important to note that these are recommendations. The specific implementation must take place on a case-by-case basis in the individual disciplines, through organisation in research projects and their researchers. Furthermore, early considerations on the topic of data economy throughout the entire research project can bring advantages, which are described in the following chapter. It is important to note that the suitability of each recommendation depends on the individual research and data situation as well as the point in time within the data cycle and must be examined accordingly. Here, data management plans are a good starting point.⁵

¹ Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft: Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct, 20.04.2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6472827>.

² AG Open Science: Mission Statement, ag-openscience.de, Oktober 2014, <https://ag-openscience.de/mission-statement/>, Retrieved: 15.03.2024.

³ Hillegeist, Tobias: Rechtliche Probleme der elektronischen Langzeitarchivierung wissenschaftlicher Primärdaten, Göttingen 2012 (Göttinger Schriften zur Internetforschung 8). Online: <https://doi.org/10.17875/gup2012-142>; Rösch, Hermann: 1.5 Forschungsethik und Forschungsdaten, in: Putnings, Markus; Neuroth, Heike; Neumann, Janna (Hg.): Praxishandbuch Forschungsdatenmanagement, Berlin; Boston 2021, S. 115–140. Online: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110657807-006>.

⁴ The term was originally coined in data protection and describes the fact that only the data that is necessary for the respective purpose should be used for the transfer, instead of simply copying complete datasets.

⁵ Hausen, Daniela; Favella, Gianpiero; Fingerhuth, Matthias u. a.: Datenmanagementpläne in der Forschung – von Grundlagen zu Grundfragen, in: Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement 2022 (1), S. 103–120. Online:

2. Why Should I Bother with Digital Data Economy?

There are many reasons for being economical in the use of data, but the main reason is the sharp increase in the absolute volume of data. For example, imaging processes and videos with a higher resolution generate larger amounts of data than those with a lower resolution. The ever-increasing computing power available for simulations and research-related computing also keeps generating ever more detailed results and thus more data.

Another reason is the increased level of demands when it comes to preparing research data for publications and archiving. Here, the FAIR principles have established themselves as a standard in research data management.⁶ Through targeted requirements, these principles ensure that data is easy to find (findable), accessible, interoperable and reusable. In order to fulfil these principles, data must be provided with detailed metadata and prepared for publication in suitable repositories. Both increase the amount of data to be managed.

Due to a frequent lack of a coherent and balanced backup strategy, data is often stored unnecessarily multiple times over the course of its lifecycle. This can also be due to the fact that researchers only trust the respective storage systems to a limited extent or are not aware of the redundancies and backups already offered by central services.

The reasons for limiting the amount of data can be divided into four categories.

2.1. Organizational reasons

Managing large amounts of data is time-consuming: In research data management, data sets have to be versioned, named, described, sorted and stored. If the volume increases, it gets harder to keep an overview of your data. If data is additionally shared externally and additional versions are thus added to your own data storage, this can increase the lack of overview. This makes it more difficult to focus on the actual research, its replication and the data required for documentation.

2.2. Technical reasons

In some working groups – predominantly in the natural sciences - data in the petabyte range is generated and managed. This data requires sufficiently dimensioned storage systems,⁷ ideally secured by a copy or a backup of the same size. In contrast to research-related computing, this resource is not automatically available again once the project is completed. In

<https://doi.org/10.17192/BFDM.2022.1.8366>; Leendertse, Jan; Mocken, Susanne; Von Suchodoletz, Dirk: Datenmanagementpläne zur Strukturierung von Forschungsvorhaben, in: Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement 2019 (2), S. 4–9. Online: <https://doi.org/10.17192/BFDM.2019.2.8003>; Strötgen, Robert: Bedarfsplanung eines institutionellen Repositoriums für Forschungsdaten, in: Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement 2020 (2), S. 112–120. Online: <https://doi.org/10.17192/BFDM.2019.2.8106>.

⁶ Wilkinson, Mark D.; Dumontier, Michel; Aalbersberg, IJsbrand Jan u. a.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, in: Scientific Data 3 (1), 15.03.2016, S. 160018. Online: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

⁷ Strötgen: Bedarfsplanung, 2020.

addition to storage itself, data transfer must be taken into account: Technical systems must be able to process, for example, image data generated by HD cameras in real time; later in the data's life cycle, corresponding data volumes must be moved to computing systems or repositories.

The acquisition, operation and regular renewal of network and storage infrastructures require technical, human and financial resources.⁸ The migration between storage systems must also be taken into account. With a ten-year retention period after the end of the project or the publication of data alone, this means almost two life cycles of a storage system.⁹ It is often unclear how these resources, which are often needed long after the end of projects or general research contexts, can be provided. The basic equipment of universities and other research institutions cannot fully provide this.

2.3. Data protection and ethics

Dealing with data protection regulations and data ethics issues is common practice in the management of research data and must therefore be taken into account in data management plans.¹⁰ Appropriate protective measures are routine, especially when handling personal or otherwise sensitive data. Ethical questions consider whether everything should be stored and processed, even if there are no legal restrictions. Once an individual assessment has reached its conclusion, protective measures are also taken. However, the greater the amount of data and therefore the greater the complexity of storage management, the greater the effort involved and the greater the need to check whether the data is still covered by the protective measures. The storage location and access rights should be decided on in accordance with data protection regulations. The risk of overlooking a version or copy of data worthy of protection, which increases with the amount of data, can be countered by reducing the amount of data: Data that is not collected and not stored cannot fall into the wrong hands.

2.4. Sustainability

The core aspect of sustainability is using resources as sparingly as possible on all levels: The provision and operation of network, computing and storage infrastructures consumes an enormous amount of resources and energy with the negative CO₂ balance that goes with it. The goal of using resources responsibly has long been common in data processing thanks to the buzzword "green IT". By limiting the amount of data, the ecological footprint of research projects can be improved.

3. Implementing economical digital data use

Even though the general point of economical digital data use is apparent, the practical implementation poses a number of challenges for researchers. In the following paragraphs, typical problems and possible solutions are outlined. Beyond that, we will show how

⁸ Leendertse, Jan; Von Suchodoletz, Dirk: Kosten und Aufwände von Forschungsdatenmanagement, in: Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement 2020 (1), S. 1–7. Online: <https://doi.org/10.17192/BFDM.2020.1.8246>.

⁹ Storage systems are usually depreciated over a period of five to seven years.

¹⁰ Leendertse et al: Datenmanagementpläne, 2019.

economical digital data use can be considered in the research data life cycle in a practical way. A checklist for checking data for potential cuts is also included.

3.1. Challenges on the way

Decision-making authority: It must be clear who has the authority to decide on the data's use. Formally, this authority usually lies with the head of a research project, but the academic reality is less clear. The actual work and therefore also the knowledge about the significance of the data often lies with other academics. Furthermore, copyrights, rights of subsequent use and possible ownership rights to data must be taken into account. It is therefore advisable to pursue a joint decision at an early stage, documented in writing and with a clear allocation of roles.¹¹

Finality: Deleted data is usually irretrievably lost. Even though in special cases there are technical options for recovering deleted data, these are time-consuming, without guaranteed success and hardly practicable, especially when it comes to large amounts of data. This irreversibility requires a well-considered and conscious decision to delete data. Such decisions should by no means be made lightly or under time pressure.

Data formats: These differ in terms of their openness, long-term accessibility and space requirements. Compressing data helps to reduce storage requirements, but it must always be ensured that data can be decompressed again in the future. In addition, processes with a high compression rate for images or videos are almost always associated with a loss of quality. It is thus important to use formats that work either without loss or with an acceptable loss of information.¹²

Technical obstacles: Storage systems are rarely completely transparent for their users. With cloud systems, for example, it is generally not possible to determine whether one or more internal copies of the data are stored on distributed servers as well as whether and for how long deleted files, for example, are still stored in backup systems. This is particularly problematic when sensitive data is promised to be deleted. Here, the operators of services are required to create appropriate transparency or to offer technical support with services such as a garbage collection. Knowing about storage redundancy allows researchers to make informed decisions about whether or not to store copies of their data elsewhere.

Feasibility: Research is very individual and so is the management of research data. This also refers to the possibility of cutting down on data or on deleting it early on in the course of research. Data that is generated during various steps of the research process differs greatly in terms of the effort required to reproduce it. This results in different options for cutting down on data or on deleting it early on in the research process. For example, aggregated data sets or text-analytical data can be reproduced quickly and easily and therefore deleted at an early stage or not even stored separately. On the other hand, raw data and data from time-intensive

¹¹ Respective regulations can be made via institutional policies (Open Science Policy or Research Data Management Policy) or individual agreements.

¹² Redaktion forschungsdaten.info: Formate erhalten, forschungsdaten.info, <https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/veroeffentlichen-und-archivieren/formate-erhalten/>, Retrieved: 15.03.2023.

simulations, for example, offer hardly any cut-related potential due to their complex and time-consuming reproducibility. For this reason, there can only be rudimentary general regulations on data economy; in all cases, case-by-case considerations with individual solutions are advisable. It makes sense to refer to the recommendations of, for example, the National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur; NFDI) for the subject and to consult with subject-specifically qualified data stewards.

Awareness: Digital data is often not visible. In contrast to file folders on an office shelf, it is a visually intangible quantity that is stored on a computer, on remote IT infrastructures or in a cloud. It makes sense to create automated reminder routines wherever possible, for example to remind users when retention periods have expired and to submit data records for a new decision on their retention or deletion.

3.2. Implementation in the run-up to a research project

The process of organizing data economically depends on many factors and must be applied holistically and individually to your own research project. It also makes sense to determine in the planning phase which data you want to keep until the end of the project and which you want to dispense with early on. You should also consider early on how many copies and versions of data are required to render your research traceable.

These considerations can be incorporated very well into the general data planning phase. Already, many research funding organizations require the creation of data management plans (DMPs).¹³ Moreover, independently from this, DMPs are recommended for all research projects: The DMP - designed as a living document - contains a detailed overview of what data will be generated over the course of the project, who must have access to which data, what technical infrastructure should be used as well as what data should be published and/or archived in the end and how. Here, you should always consider whether data is permanently required or can be deleted again.

Beyond that, a DMP-related deletion and role concept set out in writing has the advantage that it is clear to all parties involved and can be viewed at any time. It also defines who is allowed to make decisions about which data and how, even after the end of the project.

3.3. Implementation in the course of a research project

If the research project has already begun and no DMP exists, this situation can be mended retroactively in conjunction with a data economy concept. As at the beginning of a project, both require a holistic view of the data situation, from which suitable measures can be derived.

The following checklist for potential data cuts can be used before or during data collection. With little effort, precautions can be taken that make it easier to save storage space in the further course of the research data life cycle.

¹³ Leendertse et al.: Datenmanagementpläne, 2019.

When collecting data:

- Is the data stored in an organized and traceable directory structure?¹⁴
- Are the data described with metadata?¹⁵
- Should data which are only generated for test or training purposes be saved in a separate folder?
- Is data, for example from method settings or the calibration of instruments, deleted if it is no longer required for the subsequent assessment of data quality or for further research work?

At short intervals (e.g. monthly):

- Has older data become redundant or obsolete due to new data or versions?
- Are there interim results from, for example, longer process pipelines that can be easily reproduced from other data?
- Is the data suitable for publication (data quality, reproducibility, traceability)?
- Can the data be useful for other researchers/students?
- Is the data still useful in any way after the project has been completed or could it be in the future?

At longer intervals (e.g. every six months):

- How many copies of collected data exist (on the same or other resources)?
- Is collected data in acute use (possibility of archiving)?
- Have the rights to certain data changed in the meantime?
- Has the data been published (and thus made accessible) in a repository in the meantime?

Data stewards can create appropriate frameworks for such considerations and processes as well as provide qualified support for ongoing projects. Beyond that, the NFDI can be expected to create standardizations, regulations and best practices.

4. Recommendations

This article offers general recommendations on how data economy can be practiced. All recommendations should be checked on the basis of each individual or project-specific situation and adapted if necessary.

4.1. Principles

- How many copies of the data sets are required? What securing and backup functions do the storage systems used have? An automatic backup of a cloud service can, for example, make a separate copy on another storage system unnecessary.
- If data from other systems is obtained from external sources for your own research, simple redundancy is sufficient for local storage.¹⁶

¹⁴ Redaktion forschungsdaten.info: Datenorganisation, [forschungsdaten.info](https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/organisieren-und-aufbereiten/datenorganisation/), <https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/organisieren-und-aufbereiten/datenorganisation/>, Retrieved: 15.03.2024.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ If the local storage system offers the option of specifying the redundancy to be used for storage.

- Does it make sense to publish data on different systems, for example on an internationally recognized publication server and on your own university's local repository? This may be necessary as a backup if the external publication system's sustainability is not guaranteed or if you are worried about the data potentially disappearing behind a paywall in the future.
- What resolution is required for the results of data-generating processes, can compression algorithms be useful? A lower resolution significantly reduces whatever storage may be required.
- How should older data that has become redundant or obsolete due to new data or versions be handled?
- Is it necessary to save the complete data set at every intermediate stage of data processing to ensure traceability? If the steps taken can be documented and reapplied to the original data set, interim data does not have to be saved.
- When working with subsets of data - e.g. for calculations or simulations - it must be considered whether each subset must be saved individually or whether the subset can be generated again from the data with little effort.
- When sharing data with project participants, it must be determined whether they always receive a complete copy or whether data is shared in a central location.
- How should unusable data be handled? If simulations or data processing yield results that cannot be used for further research or if measurements are invalid, a decision must be made as to whether these data should be deleted directly or retained for documentation purposes.

In this sense, data economy is not a purely storage capacity-related issue, but should also become a core element of all research projects in view of ethical issues and data protection, as well as to make your own work with the data easier.

4.2. Practical examples

Example 1: Natural sciences

In the fictitious Mayer working group for environmental analysis, mass spectrometry data is collected daily from environmental samples, often in the double-digit gigabyte range. This includes data from method development, test measurements and the actual measurements, which are ultimately intended for the publication of scientific papers. To ensure that the limited storage resources are not overused, all data is initially stored in a directory organized by project. Test measurements and other data not intended for archiving (temporary files) are stored in a separate folder, which is deleted regularly. All measurement data is accompanied by a description of the measurement method used (e.g. method file of the instrument software, .txt file) so that it can be reproduced and replicated. A .txt file is also attached to the measurement data, which provides the context of the measurement as well as further information (e.g. sampling, sample preparation, measuring individuals, etc.). In addition, all of Prof. Mayer's employees are required to immediately delete measurement data that has become redundant or obsolete due to new measurements or findings. At monthly intervals, Ms. Mayer deletes the folder for temporary files and conscientiously asks all employees to check their data with regard to data quality, reproducibility, traceability and whether it could be of use to other researchers in the future, and to delete it if necessary. In this way, Ms. Mayer always maintains an overview of her working group's research data and guarantees that other people can easily find and reuse this data.

Example 2: Humanities

In a social science research project, thirty guided interviews are conducted with experts from community foundations. The aim of the study is a text-based evaluation of the survey results. The interviews are conducted online via video conferences and recorded as video files. For data protection reasons, the interviewees are assured that the recording will be deleted after it has been transcribed. Once all interviews have been completed, they are transcribed and saved in text files. These serve as the basis for further analysis. The video recordings of the interviews can be deleted after transcription has been completed.

Example 3: Biodiversity

In a research project on the biodiversity of birds, audio data is collected via recordings in a forest over a longer period of time with the aim of monitoring the number of birds present. These data are irretrievable, i.e. if parts are lost, they cannot be recovered. The data is then analysed and further processed by several doctoral students to answer various scientific questions. Initially, the data is available in an uncompressed audio format (WAV file). After processing, this raw data must still be available as a reference, with a total of more than 100 TByte, but it is no longer necessary to access this data directly.

Initially, the data was stored on a large iSCSI storage system, which was provided as a network drive via a Linux virtual machine. This iSCSI system has built-in RAID redundancy but no other backup mechanisms. The data was therefore completely copied into another storage system. This already had built-in security mechanisms, which meant that the absolute amount of data increased many times over as a result of this measure. No versioning etc. was taken into consideration, primarily the rsync tool was used for the data transfer.

After having been consulted on data management, the project management decided to switch to a new storage solution. From now on, all data that is in acute use will be stored on a secure central storage system. All data that is no longer in acute use and should only be stored as a reference is moved to an object storage system with higher redundancy and simultaneously higher storage efficiency. This step ultimately led to a significant reduction in the gross data volume. In further steps, lossless audio compression could be considered.

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